

Red Emitting DBR Laser Array with 0.1 nm Wavelength Spacing Defined by Direct Write Ebeam Lithography

O. Brox, J. Fricke, R.-S. Unger, A. Maaßdorf,
A. Mogilatenko, M. Beier, H. Christopher,
A. Knigge, and H. Wenzel

MNE2025, Photonics and Optoelectronics
Paper ID54, Session 2C, 17 Sep 2025, 11:30

Ferdinand-Braun-Institut – Facts & Figures

III-V semiconductor technologies for electronics | photonics | quantum technologies

- Research institute, founded in 1992
- Staff: 390 (headcount)
incl. 200 scientists & PhD candidates from 30 nationalities
- Excellently equipped 2,000 sqm cleanrooms & labs
- Revenue (2024): 44.5 M€
(incl. 24.9 M€ third-party funding)
- 11 Joint Labs with 5 German universities
- Part of
 - FMD – Research Fab Microelectronics Germany and
 - APECS – European chiplet innovation, pilot line

FBH gGmbH is a 100 % subsidiary of State of Berlin and a member of the Leibniz Association

Research Topics & Competencies

Optoelectronics

- high-power diode lasers: broad area & bars
- high-brightness & narrowband diode lasers
- photonic components, modules & systems (cw & pulsed): from NIR to UV spectral range

GaAs edge emitters (0.63 - 1.2 μm)

- High conversion efficiency
 - Peak values >70% (typ. 50%)
 - At least a factor of two better than other lasers
- Compactness (chip size 0.5 mm x 4 mm x 0.15 mm delivers 15 W)
- Capability of mass production, full wafer processing (3 and 4 inch)
- Easy excitation, reliable operation

Full value chain: Design, epitaxy (MOVPE), processing, mounting, characterisation, reliability

Applications of GaAs Edge Emitters

Sensing, Spectroscopy, Instrumentation

- custom wavelengths for material analytics
- absorption and Raman spectroscopy

Metrology

- atomic clocks (Cs D₂, K D₂, Rb D₂, Rb D₁)
- atom interferometry

Need for single mode, small band emission

Optical Communication

- pumps for space applications (satellite links)
- free space communication

Medicine (ophthalmology, dental)

Measurement instrumentation

- pulsed sources (LIDAR for driving assistance)
- **Multi wavelength coherent sources (surface inspection)**

Edge Emitters – Need for Gratings

Periodical modulation of refractive index
Integrated Bragg gratings – improved optical properties

- Single mode operation
- Small linewidth (kHz ... MHz)
- Small thermal tuning (typ. 0.06 nm/K)

Defined grating reflectivity
DBR type: highest possible reflectivity

**Low losses of the gratings
for high laser efficiency**

Gratings Types at FBH

Buried gratings (P. Sammeta, Poster ID 423)

- Two-step epitaxy
- Mainly DFB lasers
- Typical grating order $m = 2$
(periods $> 200\text{nm}$, duty cycle 0.25)

Surface gratings (this talk)

- Single-step epitaxy
- Mainly DBR lasers
- Grating order $m > 3$ (Periods $> 400\text{ nm}$; duty cycle > 0.9)
- V-shaped grating grooves with depths $< 2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$

Realisation of Surface Gratings

Single-step MOVPE

Hardmask

- nLOF/Ti (750/50 nm)
- Ti for nLoF patterning and conduction layer

Three level dry etch-process (RIE)

- Ti/nLOF hard mask (SF_6 ; O)
- semiconductor (BCl_3 ; Ar)

Design for functional surface gratings → **Modelling**

Influence of Bragg Order and Duty Cycle on Reflectivity

$$\Lambda = m \lambda_L / (2 n_{\text{eff}})$$

- Λ grating period
- lasing wavelength λ_L
- effective index n_{eff}
- grating order m

- Higher Bragg order gratings (larger periods) applicable for high reflectivity
- Etched groove as small as possible for high duty cycle W/Λ
- V-grooves to increase the duty cycle to > 0.9

Influence of the Etched Depth on Reflectivity

Etched groove depths 1 ... 2 μm

- large aspect ratios (up to 50:1) challenging

Relaxed process conditions with V-shaped grooves

Maximum reflectivity > 90%

Red Emitting DBR Laser Array with 0.1 nm Wavelength Spacing Defined by Direct Write Ebeam Lithography

Multi wavelength coherent source for surface inspection

Long process history: Start with 0.5 nm wavelength spacing around 905 nm

Here: Test of 0.1 nm wavelength spacing (longer synthetic wavelength) around 660 nm

- Increased penetration depth into biological tissue
- Better adjustment for holographical applications (visible light)

Ebeam Lithography

Grating dimension < 200 nm (smallest dimension in the laser process, other layers with i-line litho)

Broad portfolio of vertical laser structures with different n_{eff} (different grating periods, mask less)

Red Emitting DBR Laser Array

Chip footprint $0.8 \times 2.5 \text{ mm}^2$

- 1.0 mm active, 1.0 mm DBR and 0.5 mm p-metal pads
- Four ridge waveguides (RW) with $127.5 \mu\text{m}$ spacing
 - RW widths $3.5 \mu\text{m}$
 - Tapered RW in DBR sections ($3.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$)

Vertical Structure for 660 nm

- GaInP SQW (5 nm) with AlGaInP confinement
- Cladding AlInP/GaInP (n-type) and AlGaAs (p-type)

Ebeam Lithography and Grating Layout

VISTEC SB251 (shaped beam, 50kV)

- 3 inch GDS to DataPrep with MGS 8.4, PEC
- Dose 60 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ (ZEP)

Grating dimensions

- Single slit
 - Widths 180 nm
 - Length 3 to 9.5 μm (tapered RW)
- 10th order gratings with periods
 - 1029.43/ 1029.62/ 1029.81/ 1030.01 nm
 - Length 1 mm;
 - 971 lines, shift last line 184/ 186/ 188 nm

3 inch layout

start grating

end grating

0.000 μm 100.000 μm 200.000 μm 300.000 μm 400.000 μm 500.000 μm 600.000 μm 700.000 μm 800.000 μm 900.000 μm 1,000.000 μm

SBVis: full grating of an array

vistec
Electron Beam

Leibniz
FBH
Ferdinand
Braun
Institut

Grating Etch (I)

Targeting the precise etch depth

- Etch rate factor between grating and large area
 - Calibration factor between large area and grating etch depth
 - Statistics > 1500 measurements (XS-SEM)
- Width of the hardmask opening 150 ... 200 nm
CD-SEM measurements before semiconductor etch

Period count of 950nm reflected signal

→ Etch depth precision $\pm 50\text{nm}$ (up to $2\mu\text{m}$ depth)

Grating Etch (II)

Modelling result of 660 nm vertical structure

- Residual layer thickness 300 nm
Target grating etch depth 1400 nm
- Tolerancy with respect to grating groove etch depths

→ Etch depth on target

Yield Example: 4 Bars, 48 Arrays, 192 DBR Lasers

Coated bars with $R_{\text{front}}=0.1$ and $R_{\text{rear}}<10^{-3}$

Measurements of unmounted bars, pulse current conditions, each emitter tested separate

→ **All emitters lock to a DBR mode, all 48 arrays with spacing close to 0.1 nm**

Red DBR-Array: Experimental Results (I)

L-I-curves of four emitters of a DBR array (C-mount, separated contacts)

- Threshold currents around 60 mA and 70 mW at 150 mA
- Single mode optical spectra with an OSMR 60 dB

Red DBR-Array: Experimental Results (II)

L-I-curves of four emitters of a DBR array (C-mount; **common contact**)

- After > 1500 hours constant power 160 mW (350 mA, 25°C)
- > 4x 50 mW at 440 mA (OSMR > 60 dB)

→ **Peak wavelengths over pump current (spacing close to 0.1 nm)**

Summary

Surface grating technology is a stable method to fabricate DBR lasers with small band emission

Design rules for the integrations of surface gratings

High-order gratings with high reflectivity possible with high duty cycles

Ebeam direct write is appropriate for the definition of the surface gratings

Fast, flexible mask less way to address different laser wavelengths

Successful fabrication of DBR laser arrays with 0.1 nm wavelength spacing around 660 nm

Promising light sources for optical surface inspection systems

MNE2025, Photonics and Optoelectronics
Paper ID54, Session 2C, 17 Sep 2025

Leibniz
**Ferdinand
Braun
Institut**

Thank you!
olaf.brox@fbh-berlin.de

Please visit the poster ID 423, P. Sammeta et al.